

COMPARISON BETWEEN SCILAB AND MATLAB IN THE CONTEXT OF ENGINEERING

Gustavo L. Marques¹, João Victor A. Ferreira¹, Gustavo R. Magnabosco¹ José Augusto C. Pedro¹.
 Dr. Alexandre Manicoba de Oliveira¹.

¹Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of São Paulo, Brazil; ²Maxwell Laboratory of Microwaves and Applied Electromagnetism, Federal Institute of São Paulo, Brazil.

{lima.marques, j.augusto, gustavo.magnabosco, victor.alves1}@aluno.ifsp.edu.br e amanicoba@ifsp.edu.br.

Abstract - To assist engineers in choosing the best numerical computing software, this article compares the Scilab and the Matlab, analyzing the properties of each software in terms of cost, language, performance, libraries, and add-ons. The advantages and disadvantages of each software are also discussed, as well as situations in which they solve engineering problems.

Keywords: Matlab; Scilab; software; engineering; performance.

INTRODUCTION

Engineering is a field that involves the application of scientific and technological knowledge to solve practical problems. For this, it is often necessary to use computational tools that help in the modeling, analysis, simulation and optimization of systems and processes. Among the tools most used by engineers are Scilab and Matlab, two software that provide an integrated environment for performing numerical calculations, programming, graphical visualization and application development. However, despite the similarities between these software, there are also significant differences that can influence the choice between them, depending on the context and individual needs of each user. In this article, we will present and compare the main features of Scilab and Matlab, addressing aspects such as cost, programming language, performance, libraries and add-ons available for the software. Our goal is to provide a critical overview of these tools highlighting their specific advantages and disadvantages as well as their most suitable applications in the field of engineering.

DEVELOPMENT

Both Scilab and Matlab have similar structures and ways of dealing with mathematical problems related to engineering. However, there are differences related to costs, programming language, performance, libraries and add-ons for the software.

One of the biggest differences between these softwares is the cost. Scilab is an open source tool, that is, free, making it a very attractive option for students and university professors. This is due to the fact that Scilab presents an advanced, efficient and comprehensive environment, which provides a complete and quality experience during academic teaching. On the other hand, Matlab is paid, with its cheapest version costing 95 dollars per year. Therefore, Matlab is more commonly found in corporate environments that have specific needs and do not need to cover licenses for many computers, unlike the university environment, for example [1]. Thus, although the choice between the two is primarily focused on the specific needs of each

environment, in general, Matlab is more commonly chosen for the

work of an engineer, while Scilab for the academic teaching of one [2].

Regarding the programming language, both use easy-to-understand languages. Just like any other language, through commands, the machine transforms them into binary code and executes them through this process [1].

Using as a basis a medium-performance computer, it is possible to do 100 billion operations per second, automating the work that would be done by a person, saving time and effort [1]. To be more specific, Scilab uses its own high-level programming language, oriented to numerical analysis. This language has a very wide range of mathematical operations, mainly focused on vectors and matrices, and can include programs from other languages, such as C, Fortran, C ++, Java and Python [3].

The language used in Matlab follows a similar pattern as mentioned earlier with Scilab, with differences only in syntax and some specific functionalities, such as numerical optimization capabilities. This capability can be used for formulating optimization problems, selecting optimization algorithms, and performing sensitivity analyses, which are of great importance for engineers in various activities.

For example, when designing a metal structure, an engineer can use Matlab's numerical optimization capability to determine the optimal dimensions of the structure members. They can define design variables, such as member dimensions, and establish constraints, such as load capacity and geometric restrictions. The engineer can then utilize the optimization algorithms available in Matlab to find dimensions that minimize the total weight of the structure while meeting the defined constraints [4].

This unique functionality of Matlab allows engineers to find efficient and optimal solutions for specific optimization problems, justifying, to some extent, its cost and preference for this software in certain cases. Therefore, although the environment and programming language are similar to Scilab, Matlab offers exclusive and more optimized functionalities for specific engineering applications.

Example of syntax difference

Both codes below have the same function, which is to generate a graph of a sine function with 100 points in the interval from 0 to 2π .

```
Command Window
>> x = linspace(0, 2*pi, 100);%100 points between 0 and 2*pi
>> y = sin(x);%calculate the sine of x
>> plot(x,y);%plot the graph
```

Figure 1 – Code in Matlab

```
1 x= linspace(0 ,2*pi ,100);//100 points
  between 0 and 2pi
2 y= sin(x);//calculate the sine of x
3 plot(x, y);//plot the graph
```

Figure 2 – Code in Scilab

Figure 3 - Graphical Window Displayed by Software

In Matlab, we use pi to represent the value of π , while in Scilab, we use %pi. Another difference is that in Matlab, the use of a semicolon at the end of each line is optional, while in Scilab, we use // for comments instead of %, as in Matlab.

Concerning the performance between both softwares, it is necessary to evaluate external factors and not just the complexity of engineering calculations. In this case, the hardware and the efficiency of the specific implementations of each program are factors that directly influence the performance and speed of the process [5]. However, leaving these differences aside and considering situations where such problems are not taken into account and observing software optimization and libraries available for both, more accurate conclusions can be drawn. For example, considering that it is of interest to an engineer to do numerical simulations of physical systems, which is done a very large linear system and structure $Ax = b$, where A is a very large sparse matrix, b is the right-hand vector and x the solution vector, it is observed that Matlab is a more rational choice, as it has tools that help in this type of problem, such as preconditioning methods, CG (Conjugate Gradient), GMRES (Generalized Minimal Residual) that would deal with the problem in a highly optimized way and can solve very efficiently systems that contain very large sparse matrices. However, although Scilab is also capable of solving problems of this type, Matlab is superior when it comes to larger scales and in the presence of specific parallelization libraries.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Setting specific situations, it was observed throughout the article the difference in optimization and the greater presence of more complete and specific libraries in Matlab to the detriment of Scilab. However, Scilab presents efficiency and performance that are very competitive with Matlab. Otherwise, this article would have no relevance at all. Therefore, in most cases, Scilab meets the need for the use of software focused on numerical computation, performing many of the essential operations for an engineer, sinning only in small details where Matlab is superior, due to its greater investment in improvements and optimization.

A numerical analysis that proved Matlab's higher performance is unnecessary, as performance depends on a number of factors, including the hardware on which it runs, the specific code that is being executed and how it was written. Therefore, it would be a waste of time, considering that such differences would not affect the engineer's performance.

CONCLUSION

Based on the information presented, it can be concluded that Scilab and Matlab are software with similar characteristics, but also have significant differences to be considered in choosing the best one to use. Both offer an advanced programming environment, aimed at solving mathematical problems in the field of engineering. However, Scilab stands out for being a free and open source option, while Matlab differs by offering exclusive and optimized features. Therefore, the decision between the two will depend on the specific needs of each user, the type of problem to be solved, the cost-benefit ratio and the resources available. There is no definitive answer as to which software is better; it all depends on the suitability to each situation individually.

Comparative	Matlab	Scilab
Cost	High	Zero
Application	Academic	Professional
Integration of Methods	Higher	High
Optimization	Higher	High
Functionality	Wide	Wide

Table 1 - Overall comparison of the main topics addressed

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